

Cross-layer Framework and Condition-based Topology Control for Contested Environments*

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Abstract— There has been much work in the open literature on the use of cross-layer information and design to improve overall system performance in wireless networks operating in benign (non-hostile/non-jammed) environments. However, not much work has been devoted to developing a *systematic* cross-layer framework that lends itself well to housing alternative cross-layer design algorithms for contested networks that are of interest to the Army. In this paper, we describe a flexible, modular and extensible cross-layer framework that can be used both in contested and benign environments to design robust multi-tiered ad hoc communications networks. Our framework is agnostic to the underlying substrate and can be used both on simulation platforms as well as SDR substrates. Using this framework, we also develop a condition-based cross-layer topology control mechanism that provides the ability to create and maintain a robust network amidst hostile network jamming, and present results via discrete event simulations.

Keywords - Cross-layer Design Framework, Condition-based Topology Control, Contested Networks, SDR

I. INTRODUCTION

There has been much work in the open literature (both academia and industry) on the use of cross-layer information and design, to improve overall system performance in wireless communication networks operating in benign (non-hostile, non-jammed) environments. Thus, while several cross-layer designs have appeared in the research literature for benign environments, there has not been much work devoted to cross-layer designs for contested (jamming) environments in heterogeneous multi-tiered and multi-hop MANETs, particularly of the types of interest to the Army. Furthermore, most jamming research and analysis has been conducted with a link-level view to the problem – i.e., the case when specific links are jammed, but not with an integrated network-level view of problem wherein an area/region of the network is affected. Solutions to address the effects of jamming a network region would require multiple layers of the network to co-operate and work together. For example, cross-layer mechanisms that enable anomaly detection and adapt network topology, MAC scheduling and routing, to name a few, are all required to come together to provide superior performance in a contested (jammed) environment. Since different cross-layer solutions may be needed for different types of environment, it may not suffice (or even be feasible) to design just one cross-layer algorithm/design to solve the issues surrounding networking in contested environments.

To address the above, it is critical to have a *flexible cross-layer framework* that can provide the required basis/infrastructure to host/support alternative cross-layer design algorithms and realize them (i.e., their implementation) on a platform of choice by the Army. Observe the emphasis on the italicized words. This paper address the aforementioned critical need. More specifically, our contributions are as follows: (a) We have designed a *systematic cross-layer framework/architecture* that is flexible, extensible and robust enough to support distributed operations in heterogeneous, multi-hop, multi-tier MANETs, with and without jammers, and with and without directional networking. (b) We have developed a condition-based cross-layer topology control (CTC) algorithm to provide robust network connectivity amidst the presence of anomalies (both malicious and non-malicious).

We have realized a software implementation of our cross-layer framework (CLF) and demonstrate the performance of the CTC approach to creating and maintaining robust networks that have the potential to cater to a variety of mission objectives (e.g., robustness, network lifetime (via power consumption), etc.) using detailed discrete event simulations, as described in this paper.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a description of a flexible cross layer framework (CLF) to support distributed operations in both contested and benign, multi-tier MANETs of interest to the Army. We then describe a cross-layer condition based topology control (CTC) mechanism that has been designed to use information from the CLF to provide robust network topologies and present results using the CTC mechanism in a contested networking environment in Section III. We summarize the paper and outline some next steps in Section IV.

II. CROSS LAYER DESIGN FRAMEWORK

This section provides a description of a cross-layer framework that can be used to design and optimize performance of Army's multi-hop mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) that: (a) operate in hostile (enemy) jamming and non-hostile but interference ridden environments, and (b) employ omni and directional networking capability. Additionally, bearing in mind the need to both (i) co-exist with current systems and (ii) accommodate new capabilities as the Army brings new technologies and equipment to bear, the proposed framework caters to requirements on modularity and extensibility along with the need to enable distributed operations in order to provide the much needed robustness amidst enemy jammers.

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The concept of cross-layer design is not new; there exists a plethora of references to cross-layer algorithms for wireless networks and we cite some key prior articles [1-4]. Additionally, there also exists a cautionary note to using cross-layer design [5]. However no known techniques exist to-date that provide a *systematic framework* for realizing and implementing cross-layer designs in a *distributed* manner that optimize performance for multi-hop MANETs in a *jamming* (hostile and/or benign) *environment* with the use *omni and directional networking*. That said, much can still be learnt from the principles employed in existing cross-layer frameworks for wireless networks. Therefore, we begin by providing a schematic overview of the key concepts used to produce cross-layer designs to-date, and then propose a framework that leverages and extends the existing concepts to realize a flexible cross-layer framework that can be used by the Army to perform distributed cross-layer design and optimization of multi-hop MANETs in benign and contested (jamming) environments.

Figure 1 provides a schematic/conceptual view of a non-cross layer (left) and existing approach to cross-layer networking (right).

Figure 1: Schematic of traditional non-cross layer (left) and cross-layer approach (right)

As seen from the schematic on the right in Figure 1, existing cross-layer design frameworks allow for interactions between multiple OSI layers. For example, the Routing Layer (L3) can obtain information about the PHY layer (L1), in order to facilitate a more 'optimal' or 'robust' design. However, the information exchanges between non-adjacent OSI layers typically occur via multiple pair-wise interactions, which can adversely impact the overall system performance. For example, in contested (jamming) environments, the presence of a jammer node determined at the PHY layer will need to be communicated to all the other OSI layers as quickly as possible, in order for each layer to adapt accordingly (e.g., a TDMA MAC will need to know how to allocate slots and Routing will need to know what nodes and network areas to avoid while routing comms messages, to name a few).

Furthermore, the existing cross-layer frameworks have more of a single-platform focus and do not sufficiently support distributed/multi-platform cross-layer operations. In particular, cross-layer message exchanging mechanisms between geographically distant MANET nodes are not directly

supported. The individual cross-layer design algorithms will need to implement their own cross-layer information exchange mechanisms, which will significantly degrade performance (by requiring for enormous amounts of control message exchanges in a bandwidth sensitive contested MANET). In order to overcome the above, we propose an extensible, modular, distributed cross-layer framework that provides for efficient cross-layer information exchange both within a platform by obviating multiple pair-wise exchanges across non-adjacent layers within the platform, and across platforms via an efficient inter-platform cross-layer information exchange mechanism that provides for a compact inter-platform message exchange format that can be used by multiple layers in a platform to send out consolidated inter-platform cross-layer messages, thereby significantly reducing overheads in the bandwidth sensitive contested MANET.

Figure 2 provides a schematic of our proposed cross-layer framework and consists of the following key modules:

Figure 2: Proposed MANET cross-layer framework
Cross Layer Information & Design Manager (CLIDM) which performs the following key functions: (a) Store and Manage cross-layer information exchanges (inter and intra-node exchanges), and (b) Trigger and Co-ordinate cross-layer design (intra-node cross layer design)

With regards to (a), the CLIDM serves both as a:

- (i) *Repository of cross-layer information* – wherein the CLIDM provides for storage of all cross-layer information generated and consumed by nodes in the network.
- (ii) *Manager of information exchanges* – whereby the CLIDM coordinates the read and write access to the common cross-layer information that it houses and provides the required mutual exclusion amongst producers and consumers of the cross-layer information. Additionally, the CLIDM manages the information exchanges between remote platforms needed for distributed operations.

With regards to (b) the CLIDM performs the following:

- (i) *Relay triggers generated by control modules* to capture the inter-dependencies between control modules in the Control Module Repository - CMR (described next).
- (ii) *Initiate triggers and hence a cross-layer design sequence*, when certain thresholds have crossed, or, when certain events trigger the need for a cross-layer action. An example of the

former occurs when a nodes' lifetime (captured via remaining-battery-power) falls below a certain (user-defined) threshold. An example of the latter is when a jammer node is detected in the neighborhood in turn necessitating cross-layer actions involving PHY, MAC, and Routing in the neighborhood nodes.

Control Module Repository (CMR), which houses the control modules that govern the various cross-layer functions. More specifically, the control modules in the CMR contain the cross-layer design logic required to perform a specific cross-layer function. For example, the topology control (TC) module within the CMR contains optimization algorithms that use cross-layer information from CLIDM to initiate and manage network topology in order to achieve 'good' (and depending on the nature of the optimization algorithm, 'optimal') network connectivity.

OSI Statistics Collection Module (OSCM) which is responsible for obtaining cross-layer statistics collected by the OSI layers that is of interest to cross-layer design and storing them in the CLIDM. More specifically, the OSCM has two sets of interfaces as follows: (i) a set of interfaces to allow for interactions with the underlying substrate (DES or SDR) to allow for specification of what statistics are desired by the cross layer framework (CLF), and for obtaining them, and (ii) a set of interfaces with the CLIDM to allow for storage of statistics collected by the OSI modules that in turn can be used by the various control modules residing in the CMR.

Analytic Tool Box (ATB) which houses the algorithms used by the control modules, while performing a cross-layer design. In particular, by separating the algorithm from the remainder of the control module logic, we allow for re-use of the algorithms by different control modules. As an example, the use graph coloring algorithms can be used for conflict detection while performing slot allocations (e.g., by a cross-layer MAC control module), or for determining neighborhoods of interference (during the PHY interference calculations). Likewise, use of game theoretic approaches can be used both by Topology Control module and slot allocation modules (MAC).

Unit & External Data Modules that contain, respectively, information that pertain to a specific mission (e.g., mobility trajectory associated with a platform) and information about the surrounding terrain (e.g., DTED info).

In summary, the proposed cross-layer framework functions like a control plane that transcends the OSI layers and provides an overarching framework for the various layers both within a node (platform) and amongst nodes (platforms) to *co-operatively* interact and optimize system performance. More specifically, the proposed cross-layer framework overcomes the shortcomings of the customized cross-layer framework by providing the following key features:

- Storage-for and access-of cross layer information by all the OSI layers within a node by providing every layer the ability to 'write-to' and 'read-from' a common cross layer information storage area inside the node, obviating the need for multiple interactions to cross-layer obtain information.

- Management of information exchange across the OSI layers: (a) within a node by coordinating "read" and "write" accesses to the CLIDM, and (b) amongst nodes via coordinated message exchanges
- Distributed operations via a light-weight signaling framework

In addition, our cross-layer framework offers another salient capability. *It provides an infrastructure for different cross-layer designs to co-exist and work co-operatively in both contested and benign mobile ad hoc networking environments.* This is achieved via the 'control module repository' (CMR) feature provided by the proposed cross-layer framework.

- ❖ The concept of a CMR within the cross-layer framework is simple but powerful. It separates "cross-layer algorithms" from a "cross-layer framework", and allows for different cross-layer algorithms/designs, potentially designed by different groups to be able reside on a platform (node) and to work together.
- ❖ Furthermore, the CMR can be used to control existing OSI functionalities within a platform as the designer so wishes.

Finally, the proposed cross-layer framework is agnostic of any specific radio type as well as of any specific cross-layer algorithm.

III. CONDITION-BASED TOPOLOGY CONTROL – PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Using the CLF described in Section 2, we developed cross-layer topology control mechanisms that aim at providing robust network connectivity based on the condition of the underlying network. Figure 3 provides a high level overview of the topology control module (TCM). Recall that the TCM is one of the control modules in the Control Module Repository (CMR). The TCM is responsible for creating and maintaining a robust network topology and for seamlessly adapting the network topology in response to unpredictable/uncontrollable network dynamics. As shown in Figure 3 the TCM is designed to take the following inputs:

Figure 3: Schematic of the inputs/outputs of the condition-based cross-layer Topology Control Module

- **Objectives** – that specify the goals of the overall mission. Example objectives include Power minimization (which translates to maximization network lifetime), Robustness

(which translates to generation of a $k>1$ -edge connected network) to name a few.

- **Constraints** – such as allowable transmit power levels and # of interfaces associated with the radios deployed for the mission on hand.
- **Operating Environment Information** – e.g., information about the terrain to obtain path loss information or radio propagation characteristics in order to determine what set of feasible links can actually be “closed” (established).
- **Cross-layer information and triggers** – e.g., Jammer/Interference positions, neighboring node positions, battery power level thresholds, etc., as provided by the cross layer framework (CLF).

The outputs of the condition-based cross layer topology control (CTC) include: connectivity status and power level of the radio interface with which the wireless links in the network are created.

We provide below, a few sample results obtained with our CTC for two sample scenarios: (A) a MANET with 15nodes, and (B) a MANET with 51 nodes. Both scenarios include a jammer to study the effect of network disruptions caused by malicious activity (contested environment).

We use the following metrics (for both scenarios):

- **Connectivity**: measured as a fraction of time the network is fragmented/partitioned
- **Power consumed**: measured as the sum of interface powers of all active interfaces during the mission
- **Number of links** – as its name indicates, provides insights into the raw capacity

The above metrics relate to user-desired objectives such as:

- **Robustness** – ability to tide over unforeseen changes resulting from malicious activities (e.g., jamming) or stochastics (e.g., link quality fluctuations)
 - * Metric: “**Connectivity**” & “**Number of links**”
- **Network Lifetime** – ability of the network to provide a long mission duration, measured via the battery life of nodes/platforms
 - * Metric: “**Power consumed**”

Scenario A: Results for 15-node scenario with a jammer, for the case without and with CTC (also referred to as TC in Figures 4-9) are provided below.

Figure 4: Network Connectivity without & with CTC (Scenario A)

Figure 4 shows a plot of network *connectivity* without and with our CTC for Scenario A (15 nodes+1 jammer). The simulation was a 20minute scenario. The key takeaway from this figure is the significantly better connectivity provided by the CTC mechanism. Namely, without CTC observe that the network is fragmented for a large amount of time (top left graph). In contrast, with our CTC, there is significant improvement in network connectivity (small fragmentation time). Note also that as the number of neighbors increased from 2 to 3 (Nb=2 – top right; and Nb=3 bottom), the connectivity improves further as to be expected.

Figure 5 shows the *power consumption* without and with our CTC. To maintain brevity the key takeaway is: significant savings in power with CTC (blue and green curves) than without TC (red curve).

Figure 5: Power Consumption without & with CTC (Scenario A)

Figure 6 shows the *Number of Links* without and with CTC. Observe the significantly larger number of links without CTC than with CTC to achieve the same packet delivery ratio (PDR). Larger number of links in wireless networks in general implies more interference and lower throughputs.

Figure 6: Number of Links in the network without & with CTC (Scenario A)

Scenario B: We provide below, the outputs (Connectivity, Power Consumption, Number of Links) for a 51 node scenario with a jammer.

Figure 7 plots the *connectivity* metric for Scenario B. Observe the uninterrupted connectivity with CTC (green curve) vs. a dip in connectivity without CTC (pink curve). For this scenario, due to the high node density, the change in connectivity is not as drastic as the savings in power (Fig. 8).

Figure 7: Network Connectivity without & with CTC (Scenario B)

Figure 8 plots the *Power Consumption* metric. Once again observe the lower power consumption with CTC than without. A lower power consumption in turn will reflect in a longer network lifetime for the associated node, thereby helping the overall mission.

Figure 8: Power Consumption without & with CTC (Scenario B)

Figure 9: Number of Links in network without & with CTC (Scenario B)

Figure 9 plots the *Number of Links* metric. As before, observe the fewer number of links with CTC than without to achieve the same PDR. Recall that a larger number of links in wireless networks in general implies more interference and lower throughputs.

IV. SUMMARY & NEXT STEPS

In summary, our contributions are two-fold as follows.

First, we provide a flexible and modular cross-layer framework (CLF) that can be used in contested and benign environments. More specifically, our CLF provides *an infrastructure for different cross-layer designs to co-exist and work co-operatively* in MANETs of the types envisioned by the Army. It is architected to be easily extensible to accommodate future cross-layer designs, as and when designers come up with new cross-layer design algorithms. Additionally, it is architected to be agnostic of the underlying substrate/platform.

Next, using the CLF, we have designed a condition-based cross-layer topology control (CTC) mechanism that is aimed at providing robust network connectivity, by adapting to the network dynamics amidst hostile (jamming) activity. As shown by our results, the CTC has the ability to maintain a connected network amidst hostile (jamming) behavior and to be able to decrease overall power consumption. The latter feature has the added benefit of increasing network lifetime.

With regards to next steps, our CLF design and CTC have only touched the tip of the iceberg, per se. Potential future steps include the design and implementation of different cross-layer algorithms that span the PHY through the application layers, and implementation of the CLF on an SDR. In addition to providing a systematic basis for the design and analysis of cross-layer algorithms for both contested and benign environments, the CLF can be used with omni- and directional waveforms. We are working on using the CLF to design and analyze directional networks, as an immediate next step. With regards to CTC, some next steps include the use of dynamic/adaptive thresholds while deciding on the minimum and maximum of neighbors for the CTC algorithm, as well as linking the output of the CTC algorithm with routing to achieve better performance.

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